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An exploration of second-year students' engineering ways of thinking

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ABSTRACT

This research paper explores the role of chemical engineering curricula in engineering identity development among second-year chemical engineering students. We use Gee's notion of affinity identity as the theoretical framework, which is defined as the identity derived from engaging in the shared practices of a group. One way these shared practices manifest in engineering students is the development of engineering ways of thinking. We posit that as students participate in the shared practices of the discipline through engagement with their chemical engineering curricula, they start developing distinct ways of thinking guided by their disciplinary practices.

Semi-structured interview data were collected from twenty second-year chemical engineering students at two different South African universities. The interview questions asked students what they considered to be a typical way in which engineers think and how engaging with the curricular experiences was helping them develop this thinking. Preliminary analysis of data suggests that students described engineering ways of thinking as an enhanced awareness of real-world problems and an increased capacity to solve these problems. Additionally, students noted that engagement with the curricula makes them more curious about how real-world tools and systems work. Some students also described learning the language and problem solving techniques unique to engineering as an engineering way of thinking. Our data also suggest that not all students were aware of the development of an engineering way of thinking in them.

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1 INTRODUCTION

There has been growing interest in research on engineering identity formation with the understanding that development of a professional identity could be strongly linked with a student's retention and persistence in the discipline [1]. Research in STEM has shown that disciplinary culture has strong implications on students' identity formation. This paper brings together the two concepts of disciplinary culture and disciplinary identity by exploring how engaging with the engineering culture shapes the formation of students' engineering identity. In this paper, we particularly focus on how second-year chemical engineering students develop engineering ways of thinking through engagement with the course curricula.

We use Gee's [2] notion of affinity identity as the theoretical framework, which is defined as the identity derived from engaging in the shared practices of a group. We posit that as students start participating in the norms and practices of engineering, they start forming a disciplinary identity, which can be described as affinity identity. This affinity identity manifests in students as engineering ways of thinking.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Engineering way of thinking

The idea of engineering way of thinking stems from the work on disciplinary cultures that treats each academic discipline as a culture with its unique set of assumptions, values, and practices. Several scholars have argued that academic disciplines differ from one another in the nature and structure of the knowledge that forms the core of a discipline [3], [4]. The differences in the knowledge structures then manifest in the teaching and learning practices adopted by students and lecturers. Additionally, these differences also shape the values and beliefs of individuals and how they interact with others in the discipline, thus giving each academic discipline a unique disciplinary culture. Referring to academic disciplines as cultures, Becher [4] noted "[d]isciplines are also cultural phenomena: they are embodied in collections of like-minded people, each with their own codes of conduct, sets of values and distinctive intellectual tasks" (p. 109). Hence, engineering can be thought of as a cultural phenomenon with its own set of beliefs and practices.

To better understand the cultural landscape of engineering, Godfrey and Parker [5] identified six different dimensions of the engineering culture: an engineering way of thinking, an engineering way of doing, being an engineer, acceptance of difference, interpersonal relationships, and relationships to the environment. In their study, they found that some of the most deeply ingrained assumptions with respect to the engineering way of thinking was that engineering dealt with a tangible and quantifiable quantity, and valued knowledge was knowledge that could be used for solving real-life problems.

2.2 Affinity identity

As students enter the discipline of engineering as first year undergraduates, they start learning the engineering culture by participating in the teaching and learning processes, and interacting with lecturers, researchers, and their peers within the discipline. Participating in the various norms and practices of engineering develops an engineering identity among students.

To understand the development of this engineering identity, we use the notion of affinity identity as proposed by Gee [2]. Affinity identity is derived from a distinct set of

shared practices of an “affinity group.” Gee further defines an affinity group as a group of people dispersed across geographical locations who share “*allegiance to, access to, and participation in specific practices*” (italics in original, p. 105). Hence, by participating in the practices of engineering, students start developing an engineering identity that can be characterised as affinity identity.

Affinity identity can serve as a crucial starting point to develop professional identity in engineering students. As students enter engineering, their affinity identity toward the discipline of engineering gets reinforced through their educational experiences, leading to the formation of an engineering identity. Therefore, Stevens and colleagues [6] recommend providing students with experiences of “real” engineering work early in their careers so that they can identify with the profession of engineering. Similarly, to increase the persistence of students in engineering, Pierrakos et al. [7] recommend creating educational experiences for first-year students in engineering related activities so that they can understand the engineering community of practice and start developing an engineering identity.

2.3 Engineering ways of thinking as affinity identity

Recognizing the importance of developing a sense of identification with the engineering discipline early on in students’ careers, this paper explores the development of engineering identity in second-year chemical engineering students. For this paper, we focus one aspect of engineering culture: engineering ways of thinking.

Besides focusing on students’ engineering identity development early on in their careers, this paper also reduces another significant gap in the scholarship on identity development in engineering. The existing research on engineering identity formation has generally focussed on the influence of campus culture and interaction of students’ social identities with the engineering culture [1]. Thus far, there has been little work done on the role of the engineering curricula on engineering identity formation. This paper reduces this gap by focusing on the role of the chemical engineering curricula on students’ engineering identity formation. As students engage with the chemical engineering curricula, they start learning the shared practices of the discipline through courses and related assignments, resulting in the development of engineering ways of thinking. The following question is addressed: **How do second-year students describe their engineering ways of thinking developed through engaging with their chemical engineering curricula?**

The focus of this paper specifically on chemical engineering students’ identity formation is guided by findings from the studies (e.g., [8], [9]) that suggest that different engineering disciplines differ from one another in pedagogical methods and learning environments. As these aspects form an integral part of the course curricula, it is important to study students’ identity formation in different engineering disciplines separately.

3 METHODS

3.1 Participants for the study

Participants for this study included twenty second-year chemical engineering students from two research-focused South African universities (U1 and U2) – one historically Afrikaans and other historically English – both offering four year undergraduate engineering degrees. A total of 10 students were interviewed at each university.

Participants were sampled through purposive sampling from the participant pool of a larger longitudinal study [10] to ensure variations in gender, race, and nationality. To ensure anonymity of participants, each participant is referred to by a unique identifier in the later sections. For example, U1CHE15 refers to a unique participant (numbered 15) enrolled in chemical engineering at U1.

3.2 Data collection and analysis

Data for this paper were collected as part of an international longitudinal study aimed at understanding the development of student agency through students' engagement with their undergraduate curricula in two different STEM disciplines [10]. For the larger study, data are still being collected in the form of class recordings and semi-structured interviews done with students and lecturers. The student interviews focus on eliciting details about curricula, assessment of learning, disciplinary knowledge, students' future plans, and their overall university experiences.

This paper focuses on the segment of data collected at two South African universities that explores how second-year chemical engineering students describe the engineering ways of thinking and reflect on the manner in which their engagement with the chemical engineering curricula shapes their thinking. Probes were added to get clarification on how their thinking differed from that of their peers who were not studying chemical engineering. It should be noted that the interviews were conducted in the second half of the year and students had been exposed to a significant portion of their second-year chemical engineering curricula by then.

Interviews were conducted either in English (19 interviews) or Afrikaans (1 interview) to allow students reflect on their experiences in the language of their preference. The interview carried out in Afrikaans was translated into English after transcription for analysis purposes.

Data were analysed by Author 1 using inductive coding to identify emergent themes around engineering ways of thinking. To enhance the reliability of the emergent themes, intercoder reliability checks were conducted with Authors 2 and 3 in that they read the coded data and a consensus was reached on the coding decisions. The following section discusses these themes in detail.

4 RESULTS

Based on our data analysis, we identified five major themes emerging from the data. These themes represent the various ways in which students described engineering ways of thinking. The themes include: understanding of how things work, enhanced awareness of problems, enhanced capacity to solve problems, knowledge of engineering language, and no discernible curricular influence. Table 1 presents these themes along with their operational definitions. The table also presents how many students noted each theme to give its frequency estimate. The themes are discussed below in detail along with representative quotes.

Table 1. Emergent themes representing students' engineering ways of thinking

Theme	Frequency	Definition
Understanding of how things work	12	Student talks about having a better understanding of and more interest in understanding the industrial processes including how things are manufactured and how different tools around them operate
Enhanced awareness of problems	3	Student notes having an enhanced awareness of the problems that need to be addressed
Enhanced capacity to solve problems	12	Student talks about learning real-life problem solving including improving the existing systems and optimizing the use of available resources
Knowledge of engineering language and/or problem solving techniques	5	Student notes learning about engineering-specific language along with the distinct techniques that engineers use or the assumptions they make to solve engineering problems
No discernible curricular influence	2	Student notes that they cannot identify any change in their thinking due to their engagement with the chemical engineering curricula

4.1 Understanding of how things work

Developing an understanding how things work was one of the major themes in the data. Several participants noted that engaging with their chemical engineering curricula increased their curiosity about and helped them better understand how industrial processes work and how different things are manufactured. As one student reflected:

Looking at your water bottle over there some would think, oh, cool water bottle. And you're like, "yes, I know it is like this thing you can pull out this top." But an engineer will be like, "oh, well, do you know that material was manufactured like this and this is how the bottle works and like the air pressure, oh, but that keeps the water cold and fresh and stuff?" So, over analysing [to figure out the details] is quite an engineering thing. [U2CE1]

In this quote, the student described how engaging with the chemical engineering curricula makes an engineer more aware of the manufacturing details of objects around them as opposed to a regular user who would be more interested in the operational details of the water bottle. Similarly, another participant noted:

I can look at air conditioning, for example, and I understand the basics and the principles behind it. And I can look at sewerage works, for example, and I've got a greater appreciation for that, and the clever processes that go behind that. You open the tap and water hammering takes place and you know exactly, "okay, we can describe that, we understand that phenomenon." [U2CE11]

In this example, the student described how studying chemical engineering for a year and a half influenced their way of looking at the various tools and systems they

encounter in everyday life. They now have a greater appreciation and understanding of how the different things around them operate.

4.2 Enhanced awareness of problems

While engaging with the chemical engineering curricula helped many students better understand how systems around them work, this engagement also increased some students' awareness of the problems around them. Three students reflected on how either engaging with their curricula or interacting with their peers helped them gain a better understanding of the problems to be solved around them. For example, a student described how interacting with their peers on a field trip made them more aware of the negative impact of seemingly insignificant human activities, such as using plastic straws, on the environment:

I remember we went on a field trip, this June/July vac, and we were put into teams and we were sent to various plants and stuff. And while we were spending time together in our team, some of my team members were really passionate about this whole recycling thing, and you find out more about how what you do every day affects it. Like these plastic straws, they're a really small amount of plastic, but since they're used in bulk and transported and just manufactured in bulk all the time, they actually significantly affect pollution. [U1CE15]

The student further added that this experience helped them become more cognizant of the presence of recycle bins on university campus.

4.3 Enhanced capacity to solve problems

Besides an increased awareness of problems, participants also noted an enhanced ability to solve problems they encounter in everyday life. More than half of the participants described how engaging with their curricula has developed a capacity to solve problems through optimisation, efficient use of resources, or simplifying a complex problem by breaking it into smaller pieces. For example, a student reflected:

As an engineer, when you look at some things you're not going to think of it the same way a person's going to think of it. So as an engineer, when you think someone [without an engineering background] is thinking maybe of dirty water, they might be thinking of throwing it away, and you [an engineer] might think "oh, I can filter it and then maybe use it to water something." Or when they see maybe scrap chairs and stuff, you [an engineer] think "oh, maybe this can be used to make something else." So, with an engineer you're always trying to optimise what you have. [U1CE5]

In this example, a student compared the problem solving abilities of an engineer with someone without an engineering background. The student noted that someone with an engineering background would be keener to make an optimal use of items which others would simply throw away.

It should be noted that students' problem solving capacity extended to their personal problems as well. For example, one student reflected on how engaging with their engineering curricula helped them learn the skills to solve a complex problem by breaking it into smaller parts and solving each part separately. In the quote below, the student described using this approach to plan the logistics of their birthday party:

My birthday party was six months ago, and my dad actually pointed this out, he said to me, “you’re becoming such an engineer.” We had to estimate, there were about 30-40 people that were going to come to my party, and we were going to hike the mountain, and sleep on the mountain so it was quite a logistical issue. And we had to go and buy groceries for everyone for the evening up on the mountain. And I remember us going to the milk aisle and saying, “okay, we need to buy milk for tea the next morning,” and I said, “okay, so we’re going to have 30 people, each person’s probably going to drink two or three cups of coffee, maybe three cups let’s be on the safe side, and on average people drink maybe 30 ml in their [cup], okay so 30 times this, times, okay, we need maybe five litres of milk. Maybe, I think it was ten litres of milk. And ten litres of milk, will people be able to carry ten litres? Yes, two kilograms for five packs, okay five people.” So I think that’s a good example of breaking down a pretty abstract problem to little things, little pieces and putting them together. [U2CE3]

4.4 Knowledge of engineering language and/or problem solving techniques

Closely aligned with an enhanced capacity to solve problems in general, developing a knowledge of language and/or problem solving techniques typical of engineering was also noted by a few students. While students referred to the technical language and jargon used in engineering in general, and chemical engineering in particular, multiple times during the interview, two students explicitly noted learning about these terms through their studies. Additionally, some students noted how engineers use a distinct set of assumptions to solve engineering problems. For example, a student reflected:

I don’t want to diss accountants, but accountants might have this certain way of thinking with regards to solving a problem. They’ll have a reference book and then they’ll look at that and be like, “okay, so, there’s this problem, I apply this method,” whereas engineers have to know all those methods at once and then be very specific about identifying a problem. Be like, “okay, it’s this type of problem, I can make these assumptions.” Engineering is very assumption based. They have to be clever assumptions because, obviously, if you make a ludicrous assumption, you blow stuff up and you don’t want that. So, I think it’s very much assumption based and being very clever and sly almost. [Engineers make assumptions about] things that are negligible with regards to the greater picture. For example, if you’re doing an energy balance and there’s some change in position in the gravitational field, then you can disregard that because that changed energy that comes from that change is so small, relative to everything else, then you can disregard it. [U2CE11]

In this example, the student pointed to the importance of knowing how to decide which method is appropriate for solving the problem. The student further added that engineering problem solving requires a lot of “clever” assumptions. Describing these assumptions, the student gave the example of neglecting a small change in the gravitational field leading to a small change in energy during computing energy balances as one such assumption. The student noted that this assumption simplifies engineering problem solving without significantly affecting the final results because they are of higher order of magnitude than the quantity neglected. In this example, the student also uses technical language – gravitational field – to make the illustration.

4.5 No discernible curricular influence

While a majority of students described developing engineering ways of thinking in some form, two students noted that they had not started developing this way of thinking. However, both noted that they were aware of this concept. For example, a student recounted:

Interviewer: Now that you are studying chemical engineering, do you see things in your everyday life differently?

Student: No, I don't.

Interviewer: Do you think there is an engineering way of thinking?

Student: Yes, in fact I heard about that, but I'm not sure if I'm at that level yet. [U1CE10]

In this example, the student noted that while they have heard of “engineering way of thinking,” they are not yet aware of this cognitive development. Due to this lack of awareness, there is no significant difference in the way the student looks at everyday objects.

5 CONCLUSION

5.1 Situating the findings in literature

Our initial analysis of data suggests that students have varied level of affinity for the discipline. Most students discussed engaging in the practices of the discipline by through engaging in understanding how things work and developing problem solving capacity, evidenced through the application of these skills in everyday life. Through engagement with the disciplinary curricula, some students could also identify the nuances in problem solving that is typical of engineering. However, a few students noted that they were still not at the level where they could identify any changes in their thinking due to studying chemical engineering.

Our results also support the findings by Godfrey and Parker [5] who found an engineering way of thinking to be closely linked with solving real-life problems while working with tangible and quantifiable quantities. Several students in our study noted developing an interest in understanding the engineering principles behind different things around them and solving problems related to their everyday lives.

The findings also reflect the changes in the nature of problems solved by engineers in current times. Engineering problem solving now has expanded beyond catering to the industry's needs to include problems like sustainable energy and climate change [11]. Our data suggest that through their course activities students were aware of environmental problems such as pollution caused due to plastic and were developing an inclination to devise sustainable solutions such as recycling of dirty water and scrap.

5.2 Implications for practitioners

The results discussed above point to two major implications for curricula development. First, curricula designed to help students connect engineering knowledge to their lives can not only help them learn the course material better but also develop a stronger identification with engineering, leading to higher chances of retention and persistence

in the discipline [1]. While several students in the study were able to transfer their curricular learning to applications in their everyday lives, a few still struggled to do so. The fact that a few students who are nearly half way through their degree were still not able to make connections between their daily lives and their engineering expertise is worrisome. This suggests that more emphasis on the connection to daily life within the engineering curricula could serve the students better in terms of the development of engineering thinking and engineering identity.

Second, curricula should also emphasise the importance of developing professional skills such as ability to communicate and work on interdisciplinary and multicultural teams. Engineering work in a globalised world is not limited to just technical problem solving but also involves teamwork and communication with individuals both within and beyond national boundaries [11], [12]. However, none of the participants noted developing these skills as developing an engineering way of thinking. Hence, it is important that curricular experiences are designed in ways that help students not only develop these skills but also see these skills as integral to engineering early on in their degree.

5.3 Future work building on this study

While the findings of this study shed important light on identity development among second-year chemical engineering students through engagement with their course curricula, they also open avenues for future research. A further analysis can be done to understand racial, gender, and institutional differences in students' professional identity development. Previous research has established that students' race and gender identities interact with the engineering environment leading to unique experiences for them. Analysing how students' race and gender identities interact with the engineering curricula can give deeper insight into students' professional identity development. Additionally, researchers have previously noted the presence of differences in the academic culture including teaching and learning processes in the same discipline at different institutes. Hence, comparing students' identity development at different institutes can provide a deeper understanding of the role of academic curricula in their professional identity developed.

Analysis can also be done to understand how students' engineering ways of thinking change over time as they get more exposure to their curricula. Data are currently being collected from the participants, who are in their third of the degree. These data can be analysed to understand a shift in their identity over the year. Additionally, further analysis can be done to understand how different curricular experiences help students develop engineering ways of thinking.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tonso, K. L. (2014), Engineering identity, *Cambridge handbook of engineering education research*, A. Johri and B. M. Olds, Eds., Cambridge University Press, pp. 267–282.
- [2] Gee, J. P. (2000), Identity as an analytic lens for research in education, *Review of research in education*, Vol. 25, No. 1, pp. 99–125.
- [3] Biglan, A. (1973), The characteristics of subject matter in different academic areas, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 57, No. 3, pp. 195-203.
- [4] Becher, T. (1989), *Academic tribes and territories: Intellectual enquiry and the cultures of disciplines*, SRHE/Open University Press, Buckingham.
- [5] Godfrey, E. and Parker, L. (2010), Mapping the cultural landscape in engineering education, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 99, No. 1, pp. 5–22.
- [6] Stevens, R., O’connor, K., Garrison, L., Jocuns, A. and Amos, D. M. (2008), Becoming an engineer: Toward a three dimensional view of engineering learning, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 97, No. 3, pp. 355–368.
- [7] Pierrakos, O., Beam, T. K., Constantz, J., Johri, A. and Anderson, R. (2009), On the development of a professional identity: Engineering persists vs engineering switchers, 39th IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference, San Antonio, TX, pp. 1–6.
- [8] Godfrey, E. (2014), Understanding disciplinary cultures: The first step to cultural change, *Cambridge handbook of engineering education research*, A. Johri and B. M. Olds, Eds., Cambridge University Press, pp. 437-455.
- [9] Agrawal, A., Groen, C. J., Hermundstad Nave, A. L., McNair, L. D., Martin, T. L. and Paretto, M. C. (2018), Overriding tradition?: An initial exploration of the intersection of institutional and disciplinary cultures from the student perspective, 2018 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition, Salt Lake City, UT.

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- [10] Pitterson, N., Case, J., Agrawal, A. and Krost, K. (2019), National, disciplinary and institutional influences on curriculum: A preliminary exploration across two Washington Accord countries, 8th Research in Engineering Education Symposium, Cape Town, South Africa, pp. 607-616.
- [11] Stevens, R., Johri, A. and O’connor, K. (2014), Professional engineering work, *Cambridge handbook of engineering education research*, A. Johri and B. M. Olds, Eds., Cambridge University Press, pp. 119-137.
- [12] Dym, C. L., Agogino, A. M., Eris, O., Frey, D. D. and Leifer, L. J. (2005), Engineering design thinking, teaching, and learning, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 94, No. 1, pp. 103–120.